

Impact of Internal Control on Improving the Effectiveness of the Electronic Government Accounting System

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the control procedures within the internal control procedures in estimating the possibility of errors and manipulations in the inputs, treatments and outputs of the government accounting system. The study relied on the descriptive approach through the questionnaire list distributed to a sample of accountants and auditors of some public universities, and the questionnaire was analysed by the SPSS program. The study seeks to fill the knowledge gap in determining the areas of impact of internal control on achieving the objectives of the government accounting system, in order to ensure the quality of financial reports for the research sample. The main conclusion of this study is the existence of the impact of internal control on the effectiveness of electronic accounting system through the accuracy, adequacy and timeliness of government financial statements, as well as increasing the efficiency of accountants in electronic operation. The most important recommendation that this study can state here is the need for government units to adopt electronic operating systems in the electronic government accounting system in the presence of controls that ensure the proper implementation of these systems in order to achieve the quality of government financial reports.

Keywords: *government accounting system, financial reports, electronic operating systems, internal control.*

JEL Classification codes: *G18, G28, H83, M41.*

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Introduction

Internal control in government units is a key component of achieving transparency and credibility in financial reporting. It contributes to asset protection and ensures the accuracy of financial events and compliance with relevant standards and procedures. With the rapid development of technology and increasing cyber challenges, internal control has become an urgent necessity to enhance the effectiveness of the e-government accounting system, by providing a secure and reliable financial environment that enables decision makers to have access to accurate and objective information for sound financial and management decisions.

The research focuses on showing the effect of internal control in enhancing the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system by testing research hypotheses. The first is the

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existence of a statistically significant connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system, and the second pertains to the existence of a statistically significant relationship of influence between the two variables. The research was conducted in the government sector. The sample included accountants and auditors at a number of Iraqi universities, including Baghdad, Al-Nahrain, Al-Mustansiriya, Iraqi, Technology, and Central Technology universities, with a total sample of 200 individuals.

The study utilised the Likert Five-Point Scale to assess answers. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 28 in order to test hypotheses and analyze data. Multiple statistical tools, including Pearson's correlation coefficient and simple linear regression, were applied to determine the extent to which internal control affects government financial performance.

It is hoped that the current study would produce practical results that can help government units develop their accounting systems by improving the quality of internal control, in order to achieve the highest levels of efficiency and effectiveness in the management of financial resources and financial accountability. It is also hoped that the study would contribute to addressing the lacuna in the literature related to the role of internal control in improving government accounting systems, in line with modern technical developments and enhancing the capabilities of government units to face financial challenges.

Research Methodology

Problem statement

The growth in information technology and the large and diverse size of government units are challenging internal control to keep up with these conditions. They define procedures and methods to protect information, prevent errors, and manipulate the documentation and transmission of financial events in the government's electronic accounting system, in order to provide accurate and reliable accounting information to users. The problem can be framed with the following question:

Does the application of internal control methods and procedures lead to enhancing the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system?

Research Objectives

The research aims to:

- 1) Defining the basic concepts of the research variables including internal control, the e-government accounting system, and the relationship between them.
- 2) Determining the internal control procedures for assessing the potential for errors and manipulation in the inputs, processes, and outputs of the electronic government accounting system.

Research Importance

Strengthening the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system by providing accounting information with specific characteristics to the users of financial statements requires internal control, working in accordance with methods and procedures that ensure the protection of that information. This gives more credibility to the fairness of the financial position of the government unit, and which contributes to transparency and accountability.

Research Hypotheses

The research takes the following hypotheses as its basis:

H1: There does exist a notable statistical connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system.

H2: There does exist a notable statistical connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system.

Research Scope

Timeframe: January-March 2025.

Spatial Boundaries: The research community represents the government sector, while the sample includes accountants and auditors working in the following universities: (Baghdad, Al-Nahrain, Al-Mustansiriya, Al-Iraqiya, Technology, and Middle Technology). The community in question amounted to 200 employees.

Data Collection Methods

Research in theory was based on sources of laws, relevant instructions, books, letters, theses, and published research in periodicals as well as on the Internet. In practice, the questionnaire list identified responses according to the five-year Likert scale for the assessment of answers. Statistical treatment was performed with the SPSS version 28 program which was accordingly used for testing hypotheses and analyzing data. Multiple statistical tools, including the Pearson correlation coefficient and simple linear regression, have been applied to determine the impact of internal control on the electronic government accounting system.

Theoretical Framework

Definition of Internal Control

Based on the definition given by the Commission for the Protection of Enterprises (COSO) committee of sponsoring organization to treadway commission, the IAASB defined internal control as a process designed and applied by the management of the government unit and other persons, in order to give reasonable recognition to the achievement of the unit's objectives of credibility and reliability of financial reporting, the effectiveness and efficiency of operations, and the extent to which applicable laws and regulations are complied with. (International Federation of Accountants, 2012)

According to the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), it is a critical element in the management and risk management system of government units that are recognised, influenced and monitored by the governing body of the government unit, management and other individuals in order to take advantage of opportunities and meet challenges in a manner consistent with the risk management strategy and internal control policies developed by the department to achieve the objectives of the government unit. (International Federation of Accountants, 2012).

In accordance with IAS 400, it is also described as systems that address all financial and administrative policies and procedures adopted by the management of an economic unit in order to help achieve its objectives and ensure the regular management and efficiency of the unit, as well as compliance with administrative policies, protection of the unit's assets, prevention and detection of fraud and errors, accuracy and completeness of accounting records and the timely provision of reliable information. (Al-Amiri et al , 2020).

The primary objective of internal control is to enable automatic and continuous data processing. It provides optimal information in terms of timeliness, relevance, and accuracy, with the ability to verify its validity. Internal control has the advantage of significantly greater processing power than accounting data and effective risk control. (Zahra, 2022).

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) conducted a regional survey on the use of information technology systems in internal control systems and risk

management in the economies of the Middle East and North Africa countries. It found that the use of information and communication technology is pioneering in the middle of Arab societies through the use of data collection programs...etc.(Zahra, 2022).

Components and Elements of Internal Control

Internal control includes five categories of control elements that management is responsible for designing and implementing to provide adequate assurance that management's control objectives are achieved. These are:

1. **Control environment:** The practices, systems, and regulations that reflect the general attitude of senior management, managers, and owners of any government unit regarding control and its importance to the unit.
2. **Risk Assessment:** Financial risk assessment in reporting Management's identification and analysis of identified risks to prepare financial statements in line with generally accepted accounting principles.
3. **Control activities:** These include systems and regulations, as well as policies and procedures, with the other four components, which contribute to ensuring that the necessary measures are taken to identify risks when achieving the unit's objectives.
4. **Information and Communication:** It involves defining, collecting, classifying, analyzing, and reporting on the financial operations of the unit and assigning tasks for the assets associated with it.
5. **Monitoring:** This involves the continuous assessment of the quality of internal control performance. Management uses this to evaluate the duration of control implementation according to its specific design and to assess the extent to which it can be modified to suit changes in surrounding factors (Arens and Lubke, 2009).

The researcher believes that the control environment represents the comprehensive framework for the other components, and without an effective control environment, the other four elements will not result in effective internal control, regardless of their quality.

Definition of the Government Accounting System

Audit Manual No. (4) defined the study and evaluation of the internal control system issued by the Federal Financial Audit Bureau in Iraq as a set of tasks and procedures for processing information and data necessary to achieve the objectives of the department. These include record keeping and accounting procedures adopted in the preparation, analysis, calculation, classification, migration, summary and preparation of reports. Accounting and Control Standards Board (2000), defined the Financial and Accounting Manual issued by the Iraqi Ministry of Finance in 2013, as a system that controls the accounting control of the budget implementation process and the preparation of annual and monthly data. It also sets the rules that govern performance in accordance with the regulations and instructions, as well as includes cases of registration, deportation, classification of exchange and arrest operations in accordance with what is specified by local and international rules (Sultan and Abdali, 2024). It was also defined as a set of interrelated elements that interact It operates according to a set of accounting principles, standards and methods, according to a series of accounting processes and using a set of methods, techniques and means. (Fadel and Hashem, 2023).

The researcher believes that the definition of the electronic government accounting system is a set of interconnected procedures and elements to achieve the quality of government financial reports.

Effectiveness of the Government Accounting Information System

In light of the rapid and continuous developments taking place in information systems and their positive impact on the financial performance of government units, it was necessary to design an efficient and effective information system. The unit may be effective but it is not efficient any way to achieve its objectives at a loss, and the lack of efficiency negatively affects its effectiveness. (Muhammad and Al-Obaidi, 2024), the effectiveness of providing the type and quantity of appropriate information (Hassan and Husam al-Din, 2020), and the most important characteristics that qualify a government accounting information system to be effective are: (Abdo, 2023)

1. The accounting information system must achieve a high degree of accuracy and speed in processing the financial data of economic events.
2. The accounting system should provide management with the information necessary to achieve control and evaluation of the activities of the government unit.
3. The system should have the ability to quickly and accurately retrieve stored quantitative and descriptive information when needed.
4. The system must be flexible enough when it is necessary to update or develop the system to adapt to the urgent changes that the facility may face.
5. The system must be acceptable to the facility's employees and provide a reasonable degree of conviction regarding its importance in the facility's work.
6. The accounting information system should be simple and free of complexity, so that there is clarity in the flow of data from its sources on a regular basis, avoiding duplication of data being processed, and showing the flow of information between different decision-making centers.

The financial report generated by the electronic government accounting system relies on developments in information and communications technology. These developments have made more advanced means and tools for presentation and disclosure more acceptable to both users of this technology and government units alike, allowing them to access the direct financial report in a timely manner. (Taha, 2012).

The Impact of Electronic Operation on the Government Accounting System

The Government Accounting System plays an important role in achieving financial and non-financial performance in terms of providing appropriate financial information on the activity of government units. (Mohamed et al., 2023). In order to understand the impact, it is necessary to identify the objectives of the Government Accounting System which are: (Razouqi and Mushel, 2020)

1. Providing a general picture of the financial efficiency of the Government and its administrative system.
2. Identifying the impact of the public sector, the economic nature, the regional distribution of government expenditures, and disclosure of the composition of government revenues as a basis for planning and policy analysis.
3. Identifying government spending and revenue trends as the basis for forecasting.
4. Provision of accurate information through the rapid preparation of financial reports to the legislative and executive authorities and central economic and financial planning bodies, to help ensure the accuracy and appropriateness of actions and timely issuance of appropriate decisions. (Al-Azawi and Jihad, 2018)

The electronic operation of the Government accounting system affects the book group, transforming the book group, statistical records into folders and paper books into a set of electronic files stored on an electronic storage medium, thus diminishing the role played by public journals because it will be a by-product of the data operation process and not the main source of posting as in manual systems. The ledger may include two types, one-sided and two-sided, but under the electronic operation of data, computer memory and magnetic tapes are regarded as accounting books, resulting in the speed of recording and modification, i.e., daily books are discarded and government data become invisible. (Hassan and Ismail, 2024). This is in addition to the continuous change in the way of data collection, processing and dissemination, financial and non-financial data, the ability to handle the accounting data, which contributes to the efficiency and efficiency of accounting information, and the processing of accounting data Fast, objective, convenient, and reliable. (Ramadan, 2023). The impact of electronic operation on the government's accounting system can be limited to keeping up with rapid developments in the government's business environment, he said. There is a need for transparency in information, as well as reliability and timeliness in order to ensure accountability and improve government performance, he added.

The Impact of the Information Technology Environment on Government Accounting and Internal Control

An auditor may develop an audit program that will enable him to study the assessment of the internal control system in the IT environment and government accounting at the required quality if he has sufficient understanding of the internal control elements and the impact of the electronic accounting information environment on it, as stipulated in paragraph 16 of IAS 400: (Al-Hasban, 2009)

1. The effect of the GIS environment on internal control: This effect depends on the extent to which IT uses government accounting to process accounting applications, the type and significance of financial events that have been processed, and therein must be internal control over the appropriate segregation of duties, and access controls to software and hardware.
2. The impact of the Government accounting database systems environment on internal control: This impacts on improving the stability and reliability of data, facilitates oversight and audit procedures with other jobs related to the database management system, and should clarify the job description, procedures and criteria for the design, management and operation of the database.

The researcher believes that the adoption of the electronic government accounting system will lead to a change in the procedures of accounting control, administrative control, and internal control over the inputs, treatments, and outputs of this system, with the aim of achieving the quality of government financial reports.

Internal Control to Enhance the Effectiveness of the Electronic Government Accounting System

Appropriate accounting information has a high impact on making sound decisions. Accounting information is characterised by quality due to its specific characteristics, which are used as a link between objectives, measurement standards, and consideration when forming the conceptual framework of accounting. (Abdul Latif and Mahmoud, 2022). In order to achieve this, there must be regulatory controls that monitor the operation of the electronic government accounting system, which are included in the *Internal Control Guide* issued by the Federal Board of Supreme Audit in Iraq in 2024 under the title *General Control Controls on Electronic Financial Systems* as follows:

1. Evaluating administrative control and regulatory procedures for the management and operation of electronic financial data, through which work is divided and lines of authority and responsibility are clarified between systems, programmers, operators, and operational monitors to avoid introducing illegal modifications to data and systems.

2. Involving internal audit in the design of electronic systems and modifications thereto with the aim of establishing regulatory controls and the type of reports required from the operation of the systems.
3. The presence of security controls on all technologies used, with the provision of safety conditions such as (the presence of locks, the presence of protected doors, the presence of surveillance commands, the presence of fire alarms and extinguishers, and placing the devices in places far from water and moisture sources).
4. The Computer Systems Department provides alternative or backup systems ready to operate immediately in the event of a malfunction or failure.
5. The presence of sufficient protection methods to prevent unauthorised access, such as (the use of multiple passwords, the presence of a specific number of attempts to enter the system, and entry for a specific purpose only, such as reading).
6. There are control procedures in place for the transfer of documents and data from one location to another. They are not entered into the computer unless the authorised employee has signed them. No update or modification process is carried out unless there is authorization.
7. Conduct a trial run of the program before starting actual use to ensure that incorrect or incomplete data is rejected and use programs that contain programmed data purification procedures (health and reasonableness tests).
8. All outputs are subject to review processes before being delivered in a timely manner to the parties authorised to receive them, ensuring that second copies are available for reference when needed and kept in a safe place.
9. Internal auditors periodically evaluate information security applications.
10. Double-check the validity of the test by repeating the same process on another device and comparing the results.
11. Integrity of procedures for correcting and re-entering rejected information to detect missing data or unprocessed transactions.
12. Conducting periodic reconciliation between the different accounts in the financial systems in use, such as (warehousing accounting systems), with the financial accounting system.
13. The presence of reports extracted from the electronic operating system to verify the integrity of data entry processes and ensure the integrity of work and the absence of unauthorised practices.
14. Manually process a set of transactions and compare them with the electronic operating outputs to verify consistency in the operational outputs of financial transactions (Department of Technical Studies and Research, 2024).

The researcher believes that in order to achieve the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system, the internal control principles specified above must be available.

Methodology

Research sample

The University of Baghdad was established in 1959, while the University of Nahrain was established in 1987, Al-Mustansiriyah University was established in 1963, the Iraqi University in 1989, the University of Technology in 1975, and finally, the Middle Technical University in 2014. They are

governmental universities affiliated with the Iraqi Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and include a thousand faculty members and students. They aim to disseminate science throughout the world. They are non-profit institutions funded by the state budget and apply the governmental accounting system in registering their accounts.

Demographic Information

Table 1 shows the distribution of the study sample members according to age, academic qualification, specialization, and years of experience. As for the age cohort, the results showed that the age cohort (31–35 years) represented the largest percentage of participants, with (44) participants representing (22%), followed by the age cohort (46 years and over) with (33) participants representing (16.5%), then the age cohort (36–40 years) with (32) participants representing (16%). The least represented age cohort was (20–25 years) with (29) participants representing (14.5%). Despite this disparity, the Chi-square test (4.36), with a significance value of (0.498), did not show a significant difference between the age cohorts.

Regarding academic qualifications, the data attest to the majority of participants hold a bachelor's degree, with (103) participants representing (51.5%), while the number of those holding a diploma was the least, with (15) participants representing (7.5%). The number of those holding master's degrees reached (37) participants, representing (18.5%), while the number of those holding doctoral degrees was (45) participants, representing (22.5%). The Chi-square test (84.56) and the significance value (0.0021*) showed a significant difference between academic qualifications, indicating a clear variation in the academic levels of the participants.

As for scientific specialization, the results showed that the business administration specialization was the most represented, with (78) participants at a rate of (39%), followed by the legal accounting specialization, with (36) participants at a rate of (18%), then the accounting specialization, with (24) participants at a rate of (12%). Meanwhile, the least represented specialization was "other," with (11) participants at a rate of (5.5%). The Chi-square test (83.86) and the significance value (0.0017*) indicated the presence of a significant difference between the scientific specializations. This reflects the diversity of the academic specializations of the participants.

Regarding practical experience, the results showed that the categories (20–25 years) and (26 years and above) represented the highest percentages of years of practical experience, with (38) participants for each, representing (19%), while the category with the least experience was (6–10 years), with (27) participants representing (13.5%). The other categories were somewhat close, as the number of participants with (5 years) of experience reached (28) participants, representing (14%); those with (11–15 years) of experience reached (35) participants, representing (17.5%); and those with (16–20 years) of experience reached (34) participants, representing (17%). The Chi-square test (3.46) and the significance value (0.629) did not show any significant difference between the participants' years of experience.

Table 1. Distribution of Study Sample Members According to Age, Academic Qualification, Specialization, and Years of Experience

Variables	Details	Chi-square test	Percentages	Repetitions	Significance value
Age Cohort	20-25 years	4.36	14.5%	29	0.498
	26-30 years		15.5%	31	
	31-35 years		22%	44	
	36-40 years		16%	32	
	41-45 years		15.5%	31	
	46-and above		16.5%	33	

Academic qualification	diploma	84.56	7.5%	15	0.0021*
	Bachelor's		51.5%	103	
	Master's degree or equivalent		18.5%	37	
	PhD or equivalent		22.5%	45	
Scientific specialization	Accounting	83.86	12%	24	0.0017*
	Accounting and Auditing		16%	32	
	accounting and financial control		9.5%	19	
	Forensic accounting		18%	36	
	Business Administration		39%	78	
	Other		5.5%	11	
Work experience	5 years	3.46	14%	28	0.629
	6-10 years		13.5%	27	
	11-15 years		17.5%	35	
	16-20 years		17%	34	
	20-25 years		19%	38	
	26 years and above		19%	38	

Note: There is a significant difference between the numbers of groups for the study variable.

Overall, the results show a significant difference in the distribution of sample members based on academic qualifications and academic specializations alone, while age cohort and years of experience did not show significant differences. This testifies to a marked diversity in the academic qualifications and specializations of the participants, while the distribution across age cohorts and work experience was more homogeneous and stable.

Table 2 shows the distribution of the study sample members according to job titles in the accounting and auditing fields. Regarding job titles in accounting jobs, it appears that the position of "Accounts Clerk" is the most represented among the participants, with (48) participants and a percentage of (24%), followed by the position of "Assistant Accountant" with (34) participants and a percentage of (17%), then the position of "Accountant" with (27) participants and a percentage of (13.5%). The least represented positions are "Financial Expert" with (12) participants and a percentage of (6%), preceded by "Senior Accounts Manager" with (14) participants and a percentage of (7%), and "Accounts Manager" with (15) participants and a percentage of (7.5%). The Chi-square test (40.24) and the significance value (0.0056) showed a significant difference between accounting job titles, indicating diversity in the job distribution of participants within this field.

As for audit jobs, the results showed that the most common job was "Audit Clerk" with (39) participants and a percentage of (19.5%), followed by "Assistant Audit Manager" with (37) participants and a percentage of (18.5%), and "Senior Auditor" with (28) participants and a percentage of (14%). The least represented jobs in this field were "Senior Audit Manager" with (11) participants and a percentage of (5.5%), "Audit Manager" with (15) participants and a percentage of (7.5%), and "Audit Expert" with (16) participants and a percentage of (8%). The Chi-square test (29.68) and the significance value (0.0048) showed a significant difference between audit job titles, indicating a heterogeneous distribution of participants according to audit jobs.

Overall, the results attest to a significant difference in the distribution of job titles across both accounting and auditing fields, reflecting a clear diversity in the positions held by participants. This diversity may result from differences in the experience and skills required for each position, as well

as the variability in the job structure within the accounting and auditing units participating in the study.

Table 2: Distribution of Study Sample Members According to Job Titles in the Accounting and Auditing Fields

	Job Title	Chi-square test	percentages	Repetitions	Sig
A. Accounting Jobs	Accountant	40.24	24%	48	0.0056
	Assistant Accountant		17%	34	
	accountant		13.5%	27	
	Senior Accountant		13%	26	
	Assistant Account Manager		12%	24	
	Account Manager		7.5%	15	
	Senior Account Manager		7%	14	
	financier		6%	12	
With audit Jobs	Auditor	29.68	19.5%	39	0.0048
	Assistant Auditor		14.5%	29	
	Auditor		12.5%	25	
	Senior Auditor		14%	28	
	Assistant Audit Manager		18.5%	37	
	Audit Manager		7.5%	15	
	Senior Audit Manager		5.5%	11	
	Audit expert		8%	16	

Note: There is a significant difference between the numbers of groups for the study variable.

Table 3 provides a presentation of the results of the analysis of validity, reliability, and sample adequacy for the research variables used in the study, which include the independent variable of internal control and the dependent variable of the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Regarding the internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach's alpha value for the independent variable was (0.913), and for the dependent variable (0.853), indicating a high level of internal consistency and reliability of the instrument used. Any Cronbach's alpha coefficient higher than (0.7) is considered strong evidence of the reliability of the instrument.

Regarding sample size adequacy, the value showed KMO (adequacy of sample size) for the independent variable (0.927) and for the dependent variable (0.739), indicating that the data are suitable for conducting factor analysis. In addition, the probability value of the chi-square test for the independent variable (0.013) and for the dependent variable (0.032) achieved significant significance at the (0.05) level, which enhances the adequacy of the sample for analysis.

As for the factor analysis, the latent root of the independent variable was (3.9) and that of the dependent variable was (4.2), where a latent root greater than (1) is considered a positive indicator of the quality of the factor structure of the scale. The explained variance of the independent variable was (81.43%), and that of the dependent variable was (79.26%), which means that the research tools are able to explain a large proportion of the variance in the studied variables.

In general, the results of the table support the reliability and validity of the instrument used to measure the research variables, which enhances the credibility of the results that can be reached through this study.

Table 3. Analysis of Validity, Reliability, and Sample Adequacy for the Research Variables

Variables	latent root	probability value	degree of freedom	chi-square	Sample size adequacy	stability coefficient (Cronbach's alpha)	Number of Items	Explained variance
Independent variable: internal control	3.9	0.013	9	7,374	0.927	0.913	10	81.43%
The dependent variable is the effectiveness of the government accounting system.	4.2	0.032	9	3,937	0.739	0.853	10	79.26%

Source: The table was prepared using statistical software. SPSS

Results and Discussion

Questions for the First Axis

The independent variable: internal control

Table 4 provides a presentation of the results of the analysis of the items of the independent variable “internal control,” where the items were evaluated based on the relative weight, standard deviation, and the overall rate of agreement on them by the sample members.

Results from the table show us that the item that received the highest relative weight was (81.8%), which is item No. (10), which indicates that “one of the duties of internal control is to develop and design electronic accounting systems through the participation of the relevant departments,” with a rate of (4.09) and an SD value that amounted to (0.361). This reflects a high consensus among the participants about the importance of this role for internal control.

This was followed by item (2) which had a relative weight value that stood at (80.4%), a rate of (4.02), and an SD value that amounted to (0.378), which emphasises the role of internal control in imposing limits on unauthorised access to data by monitoring the adequacy of regulatory controls. Item (8) also came with a relative weight value that stood at (79.4%), a rate of (3.97), and an SD value that amounted to (0.341), indicating the importance of coding and numbering tapes or magnetic disks used to store data to ensure the security of hardware, software, and data.

The item with the lowest relative weight was item (5), with a relative weight value that stood at (61.5%), a rate of (3.075), and an SD value that amounted to (0.085). This item relates to the role of internal control in ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of implementing control procedures to ensure data accuracy and avoid errors. This testifies to a discrepancy in the opinions of participants regarding the effectiveness of this task within the tasks of internal control.

Regarding the item on “Enhancing internal control over the reliability of government financial statements by establishing internal control procedures to protect accounting information” (item No. 3), it recorded a relative weight (67.8%) and a rate (3.39) with a standard deviation (0.146), indicating an average evaluation by the participants.

Overall, the results show a high level of consensus among participants on the importance of internal control in developing accounting systems, ensuring cybersecurity, and monitoring the adequacy of regulatory controls. However, there were divergent opinions on some tasks, such as verifying the effectiveness and efficiency of regulatory procedures. This calls for consideration of improving these aspects to enhance the role of internal control in units.

Table 4. Item Analysis of the Independent Variable Internal Control

	Items	standard deviation	Average of 5	strongly disagree	I disagree	Neutral	I agree	I strongly agree	Relative weight	Rank
1	Internal controls limit cybersecurity risks and other breaches.	0.312	3.91	17	14	28	52	89	78.2	4
2	Internal control imposes limits on unauthorised access to data by monitoring the adequacy of regulatory controls.	0.378	4.02	17	15	19	45	104	80.4	2
3	Internal control enhances the reliability of government financial statements by establishing internal control procedures to protect accounting information.	0.146	3.39	27	27	48	37	61	67.8	8
4	Internal control contributes to keeping pace with the rapid development of information technology.	0.201	3.42	17	27	49	69	38	68.4	7
5	Internal auditing is responsible for ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of implementing control procedures to ensure data accuracy and avoid errors.	0.085	3.075	27	47	46	44	36	61.5	10
6	One of the internal control procedures is to ensure the correctness and accuracy of the data processing process after it is entered into	0.214	3.445	13	27	56	66	38	68.9	6

	the computer's central processing unit.									
7	One of the duties of internal control is to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the implementation of control procedures in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the outputs of the accounting system.	0.180	3.37	9	53	45	41	52	67.4	9
8	One of the most important internal control procedures is the coding and numbering of magnetic tapes or disks used to store data and programs to maintain the security of hardware, programs, and data.	0.341	3.97	13	15	34	41	97	79.4	3
9	Internal control contributes to preparing plans to find alternatives to deal with emergency situations.	0.176	3.485	14	44	36	43	63	69.7	5
10	The duties of internal control include developing and designing electronic accounting systems through the participation of relevant departments.	0.361	4.09	7	15	24	61	93	81.8	1

Source: The table was prepared using statistical software. SPSS

Questions on the Second Axis

The dependent variable: The effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system

Table 5 provides a detailed analysis of the items of the dependent variable “Effectiveness of the Government Accounting System,” where the items were evaluated through relative weight, standard deviation, and the overall rate of agreement on them by the participants.

Results from the table show us that the item with the highest relative weight was (80.4%). These are two items that share the same relative weight and rate, namely item No. (3), which relates to the speed of the electronic government accounting system in preparing government financial statements, and item No. (9), which refers to the flexibility of the accounting system in adapting to legal or financial changes. These two items recorded a rate of (4.02) with an SD value that amounted to (0.361) for the third item and (0.359) for the ninth item. This can be translated as high satisfaction of the participants about the speed and flexibility of the government accounting system.

This is followed by item No. (5) with a relative weight value that stood at (74.8%) and a rate of (3.74) and an SD value that amounted to (0.283), which confirms the role of the electronic government accounting system in enhancing financial transparency by identifying violations of financial allocations within the general budget. Also, item No. (10), related to the impact of training and development of accountants on the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system, obtained a relative weight of (76.5%), a rate of (3.825), and an SD value that amounted to (0.270). What This testifies to is the importance of the human element in enhancing the quality of government financial statements.

The item that received the lowest relative weight was item No. (8), with a relative weight value that stood at (67.8%), a mean value that stood at (3.39), and an SD value that amounted to (0.146). It relates to the role of the electronic government accounting system in detecting errors or financial manipulation through the separation of jobs. This gives evidence of some challenges in implementing this function effectively, from the participants' perspective.

As for the potential problems in using the government accounting system, item No. (6) came with a relative weight value that stood at (68.3%), an average of (3.415), and an SD value that amounted to (0.201). This can be seen as the presence of some observations about the use of the system during the implementation of daily financial operations, such as adopting the cash basis rather than the accrual basis.

Overall, the results show us a positive assessment of the effectiveness of the government's electronic accounting system in terms of speed, flexibility, and compliance with accounting standards. However, there are some aspects that need to be strengthened, such as the system's role in detecting errors and ensuring full transparency. This in fact invites us to focus on improving these aspects to achieve the best possible results.

Table 5. Item Analysis of the Dependent Variable: Effectiveness of the Government Accounting System

Rank	Items	Relative Weight	standard deviation	Average of 5	strongly disagree	I disagree	neutral	I agree	I strongly agree	Relative weight	T
	Is the electronic government accounting system applied in government units capable of performing basic accounting tasks correctly?	68.9	0.214	3.445	13	27	56	66	38	8	1
	Does the electronic government accounting system applied in improving the accuracy of government financial statements through compliance with	70.4	0.192	3.52	9	43	45	41	62	6	2

	relevant laws and instructions?										
	Is the accounting system applied in government units fast in preparing government financial statements?	80.4	0.361	4.02	13	15	14	71	87	1	3
	Is the implemented electronic government accounting system capable of ensuring compliance with local and international government accounting standards?	69.7	0.176	3.485	14	44	36	43	63	7	4
	The implemented electronic government accounting system contributes to enhancing financial transparency in government units by identifying violations of financial allocations within the general budget.	74.8	0.283	3.74	7	25	34	81	53	5	5
	Are there problems in using the electronic government accounting system applied during the implementation of daily financial transactions, for example, adopting the cash basis rather than the accrual basis?	68.3	0.201	3.415	10	34	58	59	39	9	6
	Does the applied electronic government accounting system provide accurate financial statements at the right time for	76.4	0.279	3.82	17	15	39	45	84	4	7

	users of these statements to make the appropriate decision?										
	How does the electronic government accounting system help detect errors or financial manipulation in financial statements by separating jobs?	67.8	0.146	3.39	27	27	48	37	61	10	8
	Is the electronic government accounting system applied in government units flexible enough to adapt to legal or financial changes?	80.4	0.359	4.02	7	27	19	49	98	2	9
	How does training and developing accountants to use the electronic government accounting system enhance its effectiveness, which in turn affects the quality of financial statements?	76.5	0.270	3.825	7	17	46	64	66	3	10

Table 6. Statistical Tests for Comparison between Demographic Categories with Respect to the Independent Variable (internal control)

Internal control		Significance level P values	Statistical test F tests	Total weight of 100 degrees	arithmetic mean Out of 5 degrees
Personal variables					
Age cohort	20-25 years	0.0313 ^s	3.303	63.4	3.17
	26-30 years			71.2	3.56
	31-35 years			81.4	4.07
	36-40 years			64.2	3.21
	41-45 years			85.4	4.27
	46-and above			92.4	4.62

Source: The table was prepared using statistical software. SPSS

Table 6 provides a presentation of the results of statistical tests to compare different demographic groups with respect to the independent variable “internal control,” using the test F and statistical significance values (P values).

First: Age cohort

Results from the table show us that the arithmetic mean of internal control effectiveness differed according to the age cohort. The age cohort (46 years and above) had the highest arithmetic mean, which was (4.62) out of 5 points, with a total weight of (92.4) out of 100 points, while the category with the lowest arithmetic mean was the category (20-25 years), with a mean value that stood at (3.17) and a total weight of (63.4). The F test showed a value of (3.303) with a critical probability value of (0.0313), indicating the presence of a significant difference between the age cohorts with regard to internal control.

Second: Academic qualification

Data reveal that participants with a Ph.D. or equivalent had the highest mean score (4.69), and the total weight was (93.8), reflecting high consistency with internal control. Diploma holders recorded the lowest mean value (2.38) and total weight (47.6). Statistical tests showed an F value of (4.087) with a critical probability value of (0.0197), indicating a significant difference in participants' responses according to their academic qualifications.

Third: Scientific specialization

The highest value of the mean value was (4.82), with a total weight of (96.4). The Accounting and Financial Control major received the highest score, followed by Legal Accounting, with an average of (4.63) and a total weight of (92.6). The lowest score was Business Administration, with an average of (2.94) and a total weight of (58.8). The F-test (5.019) and significance level (0.0374) showed a significant difference between scientific majors in assessing internal control.

Fourth: Practical experience

It turned out that participants who have experience (26 years and above) recorded the highest mean score (4.82) and total weight (96.4), indicating that longer experience contributes to a better assessment of internal control. The group with the least experience (5 years) had a mean score of (3.38) and a total weight of (67.6). The F test (3.834) and significance level (0.0295) showed a significant difference between participants according to years of experience.

Conclusion

The results show significant differences between different demographic groups with regard to internal control. This gives evidence that age, educational qualifications, academic specialization, and years of experience play an important role in determining the level of compliance with internal control practices, reinforcing the importance of considering these factors when designing and implementing control systems within units.e.(4.31).

Table 7. Statistical Tests for Comparison between Demographic Categories with Respect to the Dependent Variable (government accounting system)

Electronic government accounting system Personal variables		Statistical test F test	Total weight of 100 degrees	arithmetic mean Out of 5 degrees	Significance level P values
Age cohort	20-25 years	5.603	45.8	2.29	0.023 ^s
	26-30 years		85.6	4.28	
	31-35 years		87.2		
	36-40 years		78.8	3.94	

	41-45 years		85.8	4.29	
	46-and above		70	3.5	
Academic qualification Scientific specialization	diploma	4,215	49.2	2.46	0.037 ^s
	Bachelor's		81.4	4.07	
	Master's degree or equivalent		86.2	4.31	
	PhD or equivalent		61.8	3.09	
	accounting		73	3.65	
	Accounting and Auditing	5,731	72.8	3.64	0.034 ^s
	accounting and financial control		70.4	3.52	
	Forensic accounting		93.6	4.68	
	Business Administration		52.8	2.64	
	Other		64.4	3.22	
Work experience	5 years	3,359	47.6	2.38	0.015 ^s
	6-10 years		62.4	3.12	
	11-15 years		95.6		
	16-20 years		81	4.05	
	20-25 years		83.8	4.19	
	26 years and above		94.6	4.73	

Source: The table was prepared using statistical software. SPSS

The total weight was (86.2), followed by those with a bachelor's degree with an average of (4.07) and a weight of (81.4). The lowest rated were those with a diploma with an average of (2.46) and a weight of (49.2). The statistical test showed an F value of (4.215) with a critical probability value of (0.037), indicating the presence of a significant difference between academic qualifications in evaluating the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Figure 2. Government Accounting System

The first hypothesis: There does exist a notable statistical connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Table 8 provides a presentation of the results of Pearson's correlation coefficient analysis between the independent variable (internal control) and the dependent variable (the effectiveness of the government accounting system).

The results showed a strong, positive correlation between the two variables, with the Pearson correlation coefficient reaching (0.824), indicating that increasing the level of internal control contributes significantly to improving the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Moreover, the statistical significance value (P value) equals (0.032), which is less than the accepted significance level (0.05). This means that there is a statistical significance for the relationship between the two variables. This gives evidence of the acceptance of the hypothesis stating that there does exist a notable statistical connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Thus, the results show that effective implementation of internal control can enhance the performance of the government accounting system, especially in terms of transparency, accuracy, and efficiency in preparing financial statements and making sound financial decisions within government units.

Table 8: Pearson's Correlation Coefficient between the Independent Variable (internal control) and the Dependent Variable (effectiveness of the government accounting system)

dependent variable	The effectiveness of the government accounting system
independent variable	
Internal control	0.824 Pearson correlation = P value = 0.032*

Source: Prepared by the researcher using the statistical program SPSS version 28.

The second hypothesis: There does exist a notable statistical connection between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Table 9 provides a presentation of the results of the analysis of the effect of the independent variable (internal control) on the dependent variable (the effectiveness of the government accounting system) using simple linear regression.

Results from the table show us that the value of the constant (B0) reached 1.073, while the value of the regression coefficient (B1) was equal to 0.831. This proves that every one-unit increase in internal control leads to a 0.831 increase in the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

The results also showed that the coefficient of determination (R^2) reached 0.92, meaning that 92% of the changes in the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system can be explained by internal control. This reflects a significant impact ratio, reinforcing the importance of internal control as a key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Regarding statistical tests, the calculated F value (3.74) was higher than the table value (2.391) at a significance level of (0.05) and a degree of freedom of (199.1), which indicates the significance of the statistical model. In addition, the calculated T value (3.823) was greater than the table value (2.109), which strengthens the validity of the statistical effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

As for the level of significance (P value), it was (0.024), which is less than (0.05), indicating the presence of a statistically significant effect between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system.

Conclusion: The results confirm the acceptance of the second hypothesis, demonstrating a positive and significant impact of internal control on the effectiveness of the government accounting system. This confirms that improving the level of internal control can directly contribute to enhancing government financial performance and increasing the accuracy and transparency of government financial statements.

Table 9. The Impact of the Independent Variable (internal control) on the Dependent Variable (the effectiveness of the government accounting system) Using Simple Linear Regression

The dependent variable is the effectiveness of the government accounting system.					Independent variable Internal control	
Significance level P value	T-test	calculated F-value	coefficient of determination R2	constant		
				B1	B0	
0.024	3.823	3.74	0.92	0.831	1.073	
N = 200	tabular F-value at 0.05 significance level and degree of freedom (199,1) = 2.391 *t-value at level of freedom (199,1) = 2.109					

Source: Prepared by the researcher using the statistical program SPSS version 28

Research Conclusions

The results showed a strong positive correlation between internal control and the effectiveness of the government accounting system, with Pearson's correlation coefficient reaching (0.824) at a significant level.(0.032).

1. Simple linear regression proved that internal control has a significant impact on the effectiveness of the government accounting system, as the coefficient of determination reached ($R^2 = 0.92$), indicating that internal control can explain 92% of the variation in effectiveness.
2. Different age cohorts were found to have a significant impact on the assessment of the effectiveness of the accounting system, with older age cohorts being more aware of the importance of internal control.
3. Academic qualifications showed a significant impact on participants' perception of the importance of internal control, with those with higher degrees recording the highest levels of evaluation.
4. The "Accounting and Financial Control" major emerged as the major most appreciated for the role of internal control in improving the government accounting system.
5. The results of this study showed us that participants with long practical experience have a deeper understanding of internal control, which is positively reflected in the performance of the accounting system.
6. Internal control has been shown to contribute to enhancing the accuracy and transparency of government financial statements by implementing strict data access policies.
7. The study showed that current government accounting systems need further improvements to keep pace with rapid technological development.

8. The results showed a discrepancy in the evaluation of the effectiveness of the electronic government accounting system across different scientific disciplines, indicating the need to unify understanding and standards among accountants and auditors.
9. The study proved that the systematic application of internal control contributes to reducing financial risks and cyber breaches in government units.

Research Recommendations

1. Developing specialised training programs to raise the efficiency of accountants and auditors in effectively applying internal control mechanisms.
2. Applying modern control tools such as artificial intelligence and big data analysis to enhance the accuracy of the government accounting system.
3. Strengthening the technical infrastructure of government institutions to ensure the protection of financial data from cyber breaches.
4. Establishing clear data access policies based on authorization and multi-factor authentication to protect financial information.
5. Encouraging cooperation between accounting and control units to ensure the integrated implementation of internal control.
6. Updating academic curricula in the fields of accounting and auditing to include control concepts and the latest technologies used.
7. Conducting future studies on a broader scale, including various government institutions, to assess the impact of control on institutional performance.
8. Stimulating regulatory innovation by supporting research and studies focused on developing effective digital regulatory tools.
9. Enhancing institutional awareness of the importance of internal control through awareness workshops and seminars.
10. Establishing specialised digital control units within government units to monitor the implementation of control and evaluate its effectiveness on an ongoing basis.

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